

COMMON PROBLEMS CENTRAL ASIAN STUDENTS FACE IN ACADEMIC ENGLISH WRITING

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Abstract: The main purpose of this article is to highlight significant challenges for many Central Asian countries caused by educational, linguistic and cultural factors. Learners usually face difficulties adopting academic writing norms required by academic institutions. This article will provide the most common writing difficulties encountered by Central Asian students, discusses limited academic vocabulary, organizational challenges, citation difficulties, linguistic interference as well as cultural background differences. This paper also involves pedagogical implications to enhance student's academic writing skill.

Keywords: Central Asian learners, academic writing, EFL, writing challenges, academic literacy.

Introduction

Globalization of higher education has given rise to a growing number of Central Asian students studying at English universities. Countries, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan have largely focused on English language education system to improve international exchange and educational opportunities. Nevertheless, possessing academic writing skill is considered one of the most demanding skills ever for EFL learners. The vast majority of Central Asian students can join in higher educational organizations, still with little experience in writing academic texts in English language. As a consequence, they will have challenges affecting their academic performance.

Limited Academic Vocabulary

One of the main issues they have is insufficient academic vocabulary. Most of the students are stuck with common informal English words rather than formal one. As a result, this problem leads repetition, vague meaning in arguments. Another linked issues is that students have a difficulty with paraphrasing which is the core skill in academic writing, causing plagiarism altogether. Developing lexical resource is very essential component in academic writing.

Organizational problems and structure

Another important issue is organizational problem. Writing traditions in Central Asian educational contexts often rely on basic knowledge over structures argumentation. Consequently, they produce essays in illogical coherence. This case further weaken the overall meaning of written texts as better academic writing based on clear organization including thesis statements, topic sentences, and connected paragraphs.

Citation difficulties

Most Central Asian students do not normally practice with citation and referencing. This results in struggling with referencing styles such as APA or MLA and so on. This plagiarism often occurs because of inappropriate paraphrasing skills or misunderstanding of requirements.

Linguistic Challenges

Linguistic interference of their L1 plays a vital role in academic writing. They face challenges as Central Asian countries have different grammar, syntax, and article usage. Uzbek and Kazakh, for example do not put articles in the same way English does, resulting in incorrect cohesion. These grammar components such as word order, tenses variety, prepositions give difficulties first. Most students just translate the sentence patterns directly from their native language. By doing so, they produce grammatically understandable but unnatural sentences.

Cultural factors

In most cases, cultural identity also plays a role, affecting student's confidence and psychology. Many EFL learners feel anxiety before brainstorming, as they think in a complicated way. This may result in overwhelming stress in the process. This makes the students less creative, less critical in the discussion essays.

Pedagogical strategies

In order to tackle these problems, educators should to take several steps. Firstly, they ought to teach academic vocabulary, then, guide organizational and structural instructions. Teaching citation and paraphrasing techniques and giving continuous feedback would develop their academic literacy.

Conclusion

Students in Central Asia encounter many interconnected problems in academic English writing caused from limited inversion in academic English, linguistic patterns and traditions. These all challenges are thought to be initial stages in acquiring academic English. Central Asian students can still overcome these challenges and adopt in writing norms with pedagogical support, structured guideline and awareness about writing standards. By these, students can have opportunities to go into global stages.

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